

PHYSICAL AND ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF RAW MANGO FRUIT RELEVANT TO RAW MANGO CUTTING MACHINE

Mayur Karate¹, Dr. Kailas Kamble², Udaykumar Khobragade³¹Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Process and Food Engineering, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, India – 444104.mayurkarate@gmail.com²Associate Professor, Department of Agricultural Process Engineering, Dr. A. S. College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India –kjkindian123@gmail.com³Senior Research Assistant, ICAR-AICRP on PHET, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, India – 444104.udaykhobragade07@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Physical and engineering properties of raw mangoes are important in designing the processing equipment. The physical and engineering properties of raw mango of wild variety in Shirampur region from Maharashtra were studied. The determined properties of raw mango are used to design and development for power operated raw mango cutting machine. The physical and engineering properties of wild variety of raw mango fruit were observed. The average length, width, thickness, GMD, weight, surface area, volume and sphericity of fruit was found to be 164.5 mm, 84.2 mm, 66.6 mm, 65.73 mm, 164.5 g, 13610.72 mm², 149927.21 mm³ and 0.7810, respectively. The average bulk density of raw mango fruit was 595.77 kg/m³. The ratio of average values of pulp, peel and stone was found 25.1: 3.46: 4.22. The average angle of repose of cut pieces of raw mango observed 32.4°. The average peak cutting force require for raw mango fruit was observed 130.163 N.

Keywords: raw mangoes, physical properties, engineering properties, size, shape, cutting force, angle of repose.

Introduction

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) belongs to family *Anacardiaceae* is one of the most important fruits worldwide and is cultivated in more than 100 countries in both tropical and subtropical latitudes, especially in Asia. In India there are over 500 varieties of mango are generally extensively cultivated. Mango is grown in India in tropical and subtropical regions and grown almost in all states of India. However, it is mainly cultivated in, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Gujarat, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Orissa, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal (Bommy and Maheswari, 2016). India is a leading mango growing country and produces about 45 per cent of the world's total mango produced. It is considered as the most important fruit covering 39 per cent of area 2371 thousand ha and 23 per cent i.e., 20946 thousand metric tons of total production of fruits in the country during the year 2021-22. In Maharashtra state, the area under mango cultivation is about 157.07 thousand ha and about 439.07 thousand tons of mango production during the year 2021-22. Maharashtra contributed 2.16 per cent to mango cultivation. The major contributing districts of Maharashtra are Ratnagiri, Sindhudurg, Raigarh (Anonymous, 2022).

Mango is recognized for its attractive colour, delicious taste, exotic flavor and is known as 'King of the Fruit' in India (Bhatnagar and Subramanyam, 1973). Mango is one of the most cherished fruits, not only in flavor and taste but also for its nutritional value. It is reported that mango is a good source of vitamin A and C and rich in carbohydrates, minerals potassium and phosphorus (Shahid *et al.*, 2015). The raw mango is generally green in colour. The centre of the fruit has a single seed, which is oblong and flat. Unripe mango is sour in taste because of the presence of oxalic, citric, malic and succinic acids. Raw mangoes are also good source of B vitamins that are beneficial to maintain good health and can be used in preparing numerous dishes (Anonymous, 2019).

Raw mangoes in India are mostly used for making pickles and chutneys. Pickles are prepared commercially and in almost every Indian house and is widely popular within the country. In country many households scale pickle manufacturers have expanded into medium and large-scale units (Gaikwad, 2015). The knowledge of physical properties of biomaterials are important in providing essential engineering data required for design and development of machines, structures and equipment for handling, processing, transporting and storage of food materials (Ehiem and Simonyan, 2012). The aim of this study was to determine physical and

engineering properties of raw mango of wild variety in Shirampur region for the development of raw mango cutting machine.

Materials and Methods**Materials**

The raw mangoes used for the study were collected from farmers which grow wild variety of mangoes in shirampur region of district Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India. The collecting stage of raw mangoes selected as same for the raw mangoes collected for pickle preparation. The random 50 number of sample mangoes selected, collected and clean with tap water and then used for study. The various physical properties of mangoes were studied. The instrument used for study like Vernier caliper, electronic weighing balance, Universal testing machine, etc. used from the laboratory of Department of Process and Food Engineering, Dr. A. S. college of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri.

Methods

The physical and engineering properties like size, geometric mean diameter, surface area, weight, volume, shape and sphericity, bulk density, pulp: peel: stone ratio, angle of repose and Peak force require to cut raw mango are measured. The details of methodology of the properties given below.

Size

The three-principal dimension of the fruit was measured with the help of a vernier caliper. A Vernier caliper of 0.01 mm least count was used for measurement of linear dimensions of raw mango fruits. The longest intercept treated as length. while the longest intercept normal to length is called as width and longest intercept normal to both length and width is termed as thickness (Mohsenin, 1986).

Geometric mean diameter

The geometric mean diameter (GMD) of raw mango fruit was calculated by using length (l), breadth (b) and thickness (t) for 50 fruits from the following equation (Mohsenin, 1986).

$$GMD = (l \times b \times t)^{1/3} \quad \dots (1)$$

where,

l = length of fruit (Major diameter), mm

b = breadth of fruit (Intermediate diameter), mm

t = thickness of fruit (Minor diameter), mm

Surface area

The surface area (A) of raw mango fruits was calculated based on the geometric mean diameter (GMD) using the following equation (Torabi *et al.*, 2013).

$$\text{Area}(A) = \pi(\text{GMD})^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= \pi (l \times b \times t)^{2/3} \quad \dots (3)$$

where,

GMD = Geometric mean diameter, mm

Weight

Raw mango fruit weighed individually on electronic precision balance and the average weight of mangoes was noted. A digital display electronic weighing balance having 2.5 kg capacity with least count of 0.01g (Make: Indosaw, Haryana) and 350 g capacity with least count 0.001g was used to measure the weight of raw mango fruits, peel, pulp, stone etc. The mathematical relationship between geometric mean diameters of the fruits with its unit mass was also computed (Mohsenin, 1986).

Volume

The volume (V) of 50 raw mango fruits was calculated and used for calculating the average volume of the fruit based on the geometric mean diameter (GMD) using the following equation (Torabi *et al.*, 2013).

$$\text{Volume (V)} = \frac{\pi}{6} (\text{GMD})^3 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{6} (l \times b \times t) \quad \dots (5)$$

where,

GMD = Geometric mean diameter, mm

Shape and sphericity

The shape of mango fruit decided using charted standard method (Mohsenin, 1986). The longitudinal and lateral cross section of the mango fruits trace and compare with the shape listed on a charted standard.

Sphericity is express the shape of the mango fruit relative to that of a sphere of the same volume. It was calculated by using the following expression (Mohsenin, 1986).

$$\text{Sphericity} = \frac{\text{Geometric mean diameter}}{\text{Major diameter}} = \{(l \times b \times t)^{1/3}\} / l \quad \dots (6)$$

where,

l = longest intercept

b = longest intercept normal to 'l'

t = longest intercept normal to 'l' and 'b'

Bulk density

The bulk density of the fruits was measure using a container of known volume filled with test fruits. The bulk density was obtained by taking the ratio of weight of mango fruits in container to the volume of container and was expressed in kg/m³. The value reported is the average of five observations (Mohsenin, 1986).

Pulp: peel: stone ratio

The weight of whole mango, pulp, peel and stone weight were determined individually using electric precision top pan balance. The peel of mango was removed using hand peeler and weight of peel was taken and then pulp was separated by using knife and weight of pulp was taken and finally the weight of stone was noted down (Gaikwad, 2015).

Angle of repose

The angle of repose of cut mango pieces was calculated by using piled method. The pieces of the raw mangoes were cut using stainless steel knife of size for the pickle preparation. The cut pieces of mango were piled till the cone is formed and height of cone and diameter of cone measured. The values of height and diameter put in following formula (Mohsenin, 1986).

$$\text{Angle of repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{h}{d} \right) \quad \dots (7)$$

where,

h = height of cone (mm)

d = diameter of cone (mm)

Peak force require to cut raw mango

The main objective to calculate this force is to obtain the maximum force require to cut the raw mango fruit. The test carried out by the universal testing machine. A universal testing machine having maximum capacity of testing force 2500 N, model AG-X made in Shimadzu, Japan used. The Knife (Guillotine blade) probe was used to cut the fruit into two equal half and the values forces were reported in Newton (N). The operating speed of the machine before test, at test and after test were 1.5 mm/s, 0.5 mm/s and 10 mm/s (Gaikwad, 2015).

Result and Discussion

The maximum, minimum and average values of studied properties of wild variety of raw mangoes in shrirampur region are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical and engineering properties of raw mango fruit

Sr. no.	Properties	Maximum value	Minimum value	Average value
1	Length (mm)	194.5	118.2	164.5 ± 4.77
2	Width (mm)	94.8	70.6	84.2 ± 4.77
3	Thickness (mm)	78	57	66.6 ± 3.81
4	Geometric mean diameter (mm)	74.32	57.92	65.73 ± 3.46
5	Weight (g)	194.5	118.2	164.5 ± 17.50
6	Surface area (mm ²)	17357.11	10540.40	13610.72 ± 1446.79
7	Volume (mm ³)	215025.42	101755.80	149927.21 ± 24162.85
8	Sphericity	0.8606	0.7083	0.7810 ± 0.035
9	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	601.2	590.34	595.77 ± 1.56
10	Pulp (g)	155.9	85.2	125.5 ± 15.44
11	Peel (g)	21.7	13.1	17.3 ± 1.59
12	Stone (g)	28.9	15.8	21.1 ± 3.62
13	Angle of repose (°)	35	30	32.4 ± 2.07
14	Peak force require to cut raw mango (N)	199.136	79.433	130.163 ± 39.40

Size

The three-axial dimension of raw mangoes i.e., length of the raw mangoes varies from 194.5 to 118.2 mm and width and thickness varies from 94.8 to 70.6 mm and from 78 to 57 mm, respectively. The average dimension of the fruit i.e., length, width and thickness observed 164.5 ± 4.77 mm, 84.2 ± 4.77 mm, and 66.6 ± 3.81 mm,

respectively. Similar results observed for the length, width, and thickness by Badhe *et al.*, for Alphonso variety for raw mangoes.

Geometric mean diameter

The geometric mean diameter of the fruit of raw mango was observed from 74.32 to 57.92 mm. The average value of geometric mean diameter was 65.73 ± 3.46 mm. Similar result observed for the

geometric mean diameter by Khater, 2021 for Zebda cultivar of mango.

Surface area

Surface area of raw mango fruit was found between 10540.40 to 17357.11 mm². The average value of the surface area in samples was found 13610.72 ± 1446.79 mm². The similar result observed for surface area by Shahir and Visvanathan, 2014 for Banganapalli variety of raw mango. **Volume**

The volume of the raw mango fruit observed between 101755.80 to 215025.42 mm³. The average value of the volume of the fruit is 149927.21 ± 24162.85 mm³. Similar results observed for volume by Mon and ZarAung, 2020 for mango.

Weight

The weight of raw mango fruit ranges between 118.2 to 194.5 g. The average weight of the mango observed 164.5 ± 17.50 g. Similar results observed for weight of small size mangoes by Sastry and Krishnamurthy, 1975 for Bogadi, Sakkalli, Amlet and Suvarnarekha mango varieties. The relation between geometric mean diameter and weight of raw mango fruit is shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that weight of the fruit is directly proportional to its geometric mean diameter. The relationship can be mathematically expressed as below.

$$y = 0.0802x + 52.535$$

$$R^2 = 0.1643$$

Where,

y = Geometric mean diameter of raw mango fruit

x = Weight of raw mango fruit.

Fig. 1: Relationship between GMD and weight of raw mango fruit

Shape and sphericity

The shape of the raw mango fruit was found to be oblong and similar result for the shape observed by Gaikwad, 2015 for raw mangoes of Rajapuri cultivar. The range of sphericity of wild variety of raw mango was found from 0.7083 to 0.8606. The average value of the sphericity was observed 0.7810 ± 0.035. As the value of the sphericity is not unity i.e., 1 it is concluded that raw mango fruit has non-spherical shape. The similar result observed for the sphericity by Jha *et al.*, 2006 for Dashehari mango cultivar.

Bulk density

The value of bulk density of wild variety of raw mango fruits was observed that 595.77 ± 1.56 kg/m³. Similar result observed for bulk density by Bhalodiya *et al.*, 2016 for Rajapuri and Kesar variety of mango.

Pulp peel stone ratio

The weight of the pulp, peel and stone is ranges between 85.2 to 155.9 g, 13.1 to 21.7 g and 15.8 to 28.9 g, respectively. The average weight of the pulp, peel and stone is 125.5 ± 15.44, 17.3 ± 1.59 and 21.1 ± 3.62 g, respectively. The ratio of average values of pulp, peel and stone was found 25.1: 3.46: 4.22. Similar result observed for pulp, peel, and stone percentage by Shafqat *et al.*, 1992 for some mango varieties grown at Shujabad.

The graphical relationship of raw mango of wild variety between weight of pulp, peel and stone is shown in Fig. 1. From the graph it was observed that the weight of the peel and stone of the raw mangoes nearabout same and the weight of the pulp of the raw mangoes higher than the peel and stone weight.

Fig. 1: Relationship between weight of pulp, peel, and stone of raw mango fruit

Angle of repose

The angle of repose of the cut pieces of the raw mangoes were measured using angle of repose formula. The result indicated that the angle of repose value for cut mango pieces of wild variety of raw mangoes in shrirampur region was $32.4^\circ \pm 2.07$. Similar result observed for angle of repose by Osadare *et al.*, 2019 for Kerosene variety of mango seed.

Peak force require to cut raw mango

The force requires to cut the raw mango fruit was measured using universal testing machine as shown in Fig. 2 and results ranges between 79.433 to 199.136 N. The average value of force requires to cut the raw mango of wild variety was observed that 130.163 ± 39.40 N. Similar result observed by Gaikwad, 2015 for the puncture test of raw mango for Rajapuri cultivar.

Fig. 2: Measurement of cutting force of raw mango fruit

The graph obtain by the universal testing machine is given in Fig. 3. From the graph it observed that the maximum force requires to cut the peel and pulp transition layer of the fruit after that as the

displacement of blade precede the force require to cut fruit decreases.

Fig. 3: Graph of force vs displacement obtain by universal testing machine

Conclusions

The various physical and engineering properties of raw mangoes of wild variety of shrirampur region were studied and successfully utilize for the development of raw mango cutting machine. The average values of raw mango fruit for length, width and thickness were recorded as 164.5, 84.2 and 66.6 mm, respectively. Weight of raw mango fruit ranged from 118.2 to 194.5 g with mean value of 164.5 g. The average value of geometric mean diameter was observed 65.73 mm and varied from 74.32 to 57.92 mm. The shape of raw mango fruit was found to be oblong with average sphericity 0.78 and varied from 0.70 to 0.86. The bulk density of the raw mango was observed as 595.77 kg/m^3 . The average surface area of raw mango fruit was found 13610.72 mm^2 and varied from 10540.40 to 17357.11 mm^2 . The average volume of raw mango fruit was found 149927.21 mm^3 and varied from 101755.80 to 215025.42 mm^3 . The average weight of pulp, peel and stone was found 125.5, 17.3 and 21.1 g and the values varied from 85.2 to 155.9 g, 13.1 to 21.7 g and 15.8 to 28.9, respectively. The ratio of pulp: peel: stone was observed 25.1: 3.46: 4.22. The average value of angle of repose of mango pieces was 32.4° and the values varied from 30° to 35° . The average cutting force required for the raw mango fruit was observed 130.16 N and values varied from 79.43 to 199.13 N.

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